

Teachers' and parents' support on learners' academic stress amidst pandemic

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ABSTRACT

In response to the challenges in education brought about by Covid-19, the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) exposes the learners to different learning modalities, one of which is the printed modular distance learning. Modular printed distance learning adds to learners' workload and deprives them of good learning environments and some students are having trouble adjusting to the new learning style. Notably, if this situation is assumed, negative outcomes such as anxiety, concern, despair, discomfort, and trauma would be experienced as a result of distance learning stress. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of academic stress and the extent of teachers' and parents' support to learners amidst pandemic and is significant difference exists between the level of learners' academic stress and the extent of support given by their parents and teachers. This study employed a quantitative research design utilizing descriptive and correlational approaches. Cluster sampling was used to determine the sample size which resulted in 356 learners. Findings revealed that learners experienced academic stress, but they felt the support of their parents and teachers. A significant correlation between the learners' academic stress and teachers' and parents' support exists. This study concluded then that learning and studying at home amidst pandemics created stress and disturbances to the learners' cognitive and emotional well-being. The parents' and teachers' support to the children's academic stress was evident. The extent of teachers' and parents' support alleviated the learners' academic stress. Learners were not ready for independent learning for they needed the scaffold and guidance of their teachers and parents.

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INTRODUCTION

Covid-19's global pandemic crisis has severed societies and economies (OECD, 2020), and even educational institutions have temporarily shut down to prevent the transmission of the virus (Esposito & Principi, 2020). The most marginalized and vulnerable individuals in the educational system and all the facets of their lives have also been affected, these include poor nutrition, interrupted learning, teacher confusion and academic stress, which manifests itself in various ways: emotional, behavioral, cognitive, and physical (Rustam & Tentama, 2020).

The educational system's approach to the pandemic's learning obstacles has been anything but resilient. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) in May 2020 to provide guidance on how to deliver education during the coronavirus disease pandemic while ensuring the health, safety, and welfare of all learners, teachers and personnel of the agency designed to address the challenges in basic education posed by Covid-19. Thus, learning must continue during times of calamity, disaster, emergency, quarantine, or even war (Briones, 2020). Learners will utilize various modes of instruction in the comfort of their own homes, ensuring that no one is left behind while prioritizing their health and safety from an unknown virus. BELCP ensures that the learning continuity through K-12 curriculum adjustments, alignment of learning materials, deployment of multiple learning delivery modalities, provision of corresponding training for teachers and school leaders, and proper orientation of parents or guardians of learners (DepEd Order No.12, s. 2020).

In most public schools in the Philippines, Pupils are being inundated with additional workloads through modular printed distance learning, increasing their burden and resulting in a lack of conducive learning environments at home (Bagayas, 2020). Some students who lack resources have difficulty adjusting to the new mode of instruction (Dollanganger, 2020), this situation harms the learners' mental health, and when things are taken for granted, anxiety, worries, depression, distress, and trauma occur, consequent to the stresses caused by distance learning (Rifareal, 2020). Mahuro & Hungi (2016) asserted that education research integrates various academic outcomes with parental involvement in child education. Parental involvement entails devoting time and resources to their children's academic performance. The findings indicate that increasing parental involvement through parenting and communication improves learners' numeracy and literacy scores. Thus, parenting is critical in encouraging children to increase their academic credentials.

In this context, the researchers were motivated to assess the level of learners' academic stress and the support provided by teachers and parents for learners who study at home from afar and their experienced academic stress during the transition period in the so-called new normal education delivery.

OBJECTIVES

This study aimed to determine the teachers' and parents' support on academic stress of learners studying from home enrolled in elementary schools in the Division of Cadiz City in the school year 2020-2021 amidst pandemic. Specifically, this study sought to answer the level of learners' academic stress in terms of behavioural stress, emotional stress, physical stress, and cognitive stress, as well as the extent of teachers' and parents' support on learners' academic stress. Also to determine if there is significant difference in the extent of teachers' and parents' support on academic. Lastly the researchers also wanted to see if there is a significant correlation between students' academic stress and their teachers' and parents' support.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research method, incorporating both descriptive and correlational designs. The descriptive approach described the level of academic stress experienced by learners during the

pandemic and the extent to which teachers and parents supported the learners. On the other hand, the correlational approach determined a relationship between academic stress and teachers' support and parents' support.

Respondents

The respondents were 356 grade-six learners out of the total population of 2, 446 in the Division of Cadiz City, school year 2020-2021. Cluster sampling was used since there is still an existing pandemic during the conduct of the study and cluster sampling uses randomization having high external validity since the sample will reflect the characteristics of the population. In obtaining this data, the population was divided by seven (7) clusters to represent the seven districts in the Division, approximately 350 learners per district were obtained. The learners per district were divided by the sample size, which resulted in 0.983. Hence, the 356 participants can be taken from any of the districts. Simple random sampling utilizing the fishbowl technique was used which led to the selection of District 7. The number of participants per school from the District was randomly selected using stratified random sampling.

Instrument

This study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire that made use of a five-point Likert Scale in recording responses. Three sets of questionnaire was used in this study, one set was for the learners, another was set for the parents and the third set was for the teachers. The first part of the questionnaire for the learners was used to determine the level of academic stress of learners in terms of four aspects, namely behavioural, emotional, physical, and cognitive and the second part of the questionnaire was used to determine the extent of teachers' and parents' support to learners' academic stress amidst pandemic. The questionnaires for the parents and the teachers were used to determine the extent of their support to the learners' academic stress.

The answers were evaluated through a five-point Likert scale. The weighted mean and its interpretation are found below:

Scale	Range - Value			Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21	-	5.00	Very High
4	3.41	-	4.20	High
3	2.61	-	3.40	Moderately
2	1.81	-	2.60	Low
1	1.00	-	1.80	Very Low

The answers of the teachers and parents on the questionnaire, which assess the extent of teachers' and parents' support to the learners amidst pandemic, was evaluated through a five-point Likert scale. The weighted mean and its interpretation are found below:

Scale	Range - Value			Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21	-	5.00	Very High Extent
4	3.41	-	4.20	High Extent
3	2.61	-	3.40	Moderately Extent
2	1.81	-	2.60	Low Extent
1	1.00	-	1.80	Very Low Extent

Data Gathering Procedure

With the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study the researchers conducted an orientation about the objectives of the study and the confidentiality of all information provided in the questionnaire, including their responses. Observing the required proper health protocols the survey questionnaires were distributed and accomplished survey questionnaires were gathered immediately.

Ethical Consideration

The inclusion of the respondents in this study was voluntary and no compensation was provided to the participants. Since the learner- respondents were underage, informed consent for human participation in research was secured. The participants' privacy and identity were held protected by the researchers by not naming the participants in the study and removal of identifier components such as residence and schools enrolled were observed and their answers to the survey questionnaire were guaranteed full confidentiality.

Data Analysis

In achieving the objective of the study, the data obtained using questionnaires was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. In order to identify the level of academic stress, extent of teachers' and parents' support on the academic stress of the learners, mean and standard deviation were used. To determine significant differences in the extent of teachers' and parents' support on academic stress, t-test for independent samples was employed and to determine the significant correlation Pearson Product Moment of Correlation was applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussion of the data collected and is presented using tabular presentation, which consists of the findings in this study such as the Level of Learners' Academic Stress, Extent of Teachers' Support on Learners' Academic Stress, Extent of Parents' Support on Learners' Academic Stress Amidst the Pandemic, The difference in the Extent of Teachers' Support as Assessed by the Learners and the Teachers, The difference in the Extent of Parents' Support as assessed by the Learners and the Parents Correlation Between Learners' Academic Stress and Teachers' Support, Correlation Between Learners' Academic Stress and Parents' Support.

Table 1. Level of learners' academic stress

Academic Stress	Central School (n =114)			Non-Central School (n = 242)			As a whole (n = 356)			
	SD	Mean	VI	SD	Mean	VI	SD	Mean	VI	
Behavioral										
I have difficulty completing the tasks and activities in the module.	1.104	3.05	M	1.036	3.02	M	1.057	3.03	M	
I easily get irritated, have outbursts of anger, and have frequent arguments with the people around me when they remind me of answering the module.	1.162	2.85	M	1.272	2.71	M	1.238	2.76	M	
I have irregular sleeping time since I study from home.	1.208	2.68	M	1.315	2.76	M	1.281	2.73	M	
I have periods of crying while studying from home.	1.431	2.40	L	1.334	2.41	L	1.364	2.41	L	
I feel lazy and procrastinate in answering the module.	1.314	2.91	M	1.246	2.90	M	1.267	2.90	M	
Mean of Means	0.855	2.78	M	0.884	2.76	M	0.874	2.77	M	
Emotional										
I get upset about the many demands in answering the modules.	1.182	2.98	M	1.280	3.00	M	1.248	3.00	M	
I have negative feelings while studying at home.	1.140	2.96	M	1.182	2.79	M	1.170	2.84	M	
I feel scared of answering the modules.	1.216	2.91	M	1.282	2.48	L	1.276	2.62	M	
I feel helpless in studying at home.	1.189	2.83	M	1.221	2.57	L	1.215	2.66	M	
I feel that I do not like the challenges in learning at home.	1.083	2.53	L	1.261	2.67	M	1.207	2.63	M	
Mean of Means	0.879	2.84	M	0.955	2.70	M	0.932	2.75	M	
Physical										
I am tired of getting up in the morning and following my daily class schedule routine.	1.325	2.85	M	1.197	2.64	M	1.242	2.71	M	
I experienced a headache in answering the modules.	1.212	2.90	M	1.293	2.62	M	1.273	2.71	M	
I have household chores to do aside from studying and answering my modules at home.	1.101	3.72	H	1.167	3.45	H	1.151	3.54	H	
I am physically exhausted from answering the modules.	1.111	2.93	M	1.274	2.77	M	1.225	2.82	M	
I get chills when I answer my modules.	1.303	2.43	L	1.250	2.28	L	1.267	2.33	L	
Mean of Means	0.817	2.97	M	0.845	2.75	M	0.841	2.82	M	
Cognitive										
I am confused about accomplishing the modules because some of the activities are	1.191	3.46	H	1.255	3.39	M	1.234	3.42	H	

difficult to understand.

I constantly forget to answer the modules.	1.297	2.77	M	1.255	2.69	M	1.268	2.72	M
I have difficulty focusing and concentrating in studying the modules.	1.111	3.29	M	1.151	3.05	M	1.142	3.13	M
I think of the negative sides of answering the module.	1.265	2.89	M	1.256	2.83	M	1.257	2.85	M
I have a problem in thinking, analyzing, and making decisions in the module given to me.	1.199	2.94	M	1.302	2.84	M	1.269	2.87	M
Mean of Means	0.868	3.07	M	0.881	2.96	M	0.877	3.00	M
Grand Mean	0.548	3.27	M	0.531	3.11	M	0.541	3.16	M

SD = Standard Deviation

VI = Verbal Interpretation

As a whole, elementary learners have moderate level of academic stress ($M = 3.16$; $SD = 0.541$). It is revealed that regardless of type of school of learners their level of academic stress is moderate. Remote learning brought lots of challenges and difficulties to learners and is associated with academic stress, may it be behaviourally, emotionally, physically, and cognitively. Coping with the new setup of learning modality like, multiple distance learning delivery modality might also become a challenge for the learners. Additionally, this confirms the findings of Perino (2007), as cited in Hukom & Madrigal (2020), that senior high school students experience a moderate level of academic stress. As a Whole and regardless of the type of school, the learners exhibit a moderate level of stress in all parameters. Cognitive stress obtained the highest mean score ($M = 3.00$; $SD = 0.877$) and when learners were categorized into school type. Emotional stress obtained the lowest mean score ($M = 2.75$; $SD = 0.932$) as a whole and for non-central school learners ($M = 2.70$; $SD = 0.955$); while, central school learners obtained the lowest mean score in behavioral stress ($M = 2.78$; $SD = 0.855$).

Results indicated that, learners experienced more stress in terms of cognitive aspect and less stress in emotional aspect for non-central school learners and in-terms of behavioral aspect for central school learners. It can be asserted that it is due to the bulks of modules they need to accomplish and pass within the required weekly schedule. Specifically, in terms of behavioural stress, the learners are moderately stressed in all items except for item number 4 (I have periods of crying while studying from home), with an obtained mean score of 2.41 and standard deviation of 1.364 interpreted as low-stress level. Moreover, in terms of emotional stress, learners from non-central schools experience low levels of stress in items 3 and 4 (I feel scared of answering the modules and I feel helpless in studying at home); while learners from the central school have low level of stress in item number 5 (I feel that I do not like the challenges in learning at home).

In terms of physical stress, it can be gleaned from Table 1 that, as a whole and whether learners are categorized according to their type of school, they experienced high level of stress in having household chores to do aside from studying and answering modules at home; they exhibit a lower level of stress in getting chills when answering their modules. Lastly, central school learners experienced a high level of cognitive stress since they were confused in accomplishing modules because some of the activities were difficult to understand, this is corroborated by Schneck (2020), who stated that while everyone has been impacted by the outbreak, learners, in particular, have experienced an abnormal amount of uncertainty, worry, boredom, loneliness, and instability. Remote education, social exclusion, and a general sense of insecurity about educational, social, and professional life were all contributory to the declining mental health and probably the most debilitating mental health effect of the virus was a sense of chronic tension, anxiety, and widespread suspicion throughout the country. When combined with a lack of discipline and regularity, anxious and gloomy perspective can damage the adolescents' social, intellectual, and emotional development. The pandemic's worry presents itself in a variety of ways: socially, academically, and individually. The anxiety consequent to the pandemic manifests in various mindsets: personally, socially, and academically.

Table 2. *Extent of teachers' support on learners amidst the pandemic*

Teacher's Support	Learners*						Teachers**					
	Central School (n =114)		Non-Central School (n = 242)		As a whole		Central School (n =114)		Non-Central School (n = 242)		As a whole	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Understandable instruction and clear work in the module are given and set.	4.17	HE	3.87	HE	3.97	HE	4.89	VHE	4.64	VHE	4.7	VHE
Conducts home visitation regularly to follow up activities in the learning module.	3.69	HE	3.68	HE	3.68	HE	4.65	VHE	4.41	VHE	4.4	VHE
Gives immediate feedback on the work done or completed.	3.85	HE	3.52	HE	3.63	HE	4.58	VHE	4.35	VHE	4.4	VHE
Always remind me of the tasks in the module to be completed for the week.	4.09	HE	3.85	HE	3.92	HE	4.87	VHE	4.52	VHE	4.6	VHE
Makes sure that the scheduled class program on studying from home is followed.	3.98	HE	3.76	HE	3.83	HE	4.77	VHE	4.44	VHE	4.5	VHE
Gives additional resources (online interactive games, videos, articles) to further understand what is in the module.	3.94	HE	3.52	HE	3.66	HE	3.78	HE	3.83	HE	3.8	HE
Raising questions and concerns about the modules in an available communication platform.	3.87	HE	3.66	HE	3.71	HE	4.61	VHE	4.42	VHE	4.4	VHE
Asks feelings and ideas about the module at hand (i.e. if it's difficult or easy).	3.99	HE	3.55	HE	3.69	HE	3.87	HE	4.20	HE	4.0	HE

Have enough time available for learners who are struggling to answer the modules by directing them what to do and how to accomplish it.	3.93	HE	3.53	HE	3.66	HE	4.57	VHE	4.38	VHE	4.4	VHE
											4	
Collaborates with learners' parents on the study-from-home scheme.	4.24	VH E	3.98	HE	3.86	HE	4.89	VHE	4.50	VHE	4.6	VHE
											2	
Grand Mean	3.97	HE	3.68	HE	3.77	HE	4.55	VHE	4.37	VHE	4.4	VHE
											3	

SD = Standard Deviation
VI = Verbal Interpretation

Table 2 expresses that learners perceived their teachers' support to a high extent ($M = 3.77$), while teachers perceived they had supported their learners to a very high extent ($M = 4.43$). This is manifested in 9 out of ten indicators of teachers support presented in the table. It can be asserted that teachers responded to the need of the learners in some aspects in their remote learning, but it was felt or less likely seen by the learners. It is only in terms of giving additional resources to further understand the modules that teachers and learners display similar perceptions. Both teachers and learners assessed this support to a high extent. Whereas gaining teachers' support is essential for learners' learning. However, learners 'surveyed, it is still a difficulty, thus resulting in limited teacher scaffolds. This is supported by Rotas & Cahapay (2020), who found that sometimes professors' expectations of students were difficult to achieve, making them difficult to approach. Remote learning, like on-campus learning, requires social interaction and sharing of ideas. Baticulon et al. (2020) and Sarvestani et al. (2020) posited that learners struggle with distance learning because of inadequate communication among them, they asserted that societal issues such as these influence students' motivation and intention to study online. Gaur, Sharma, and Mudgal (2020) reported a comparable absence of discussion among students in nursing online classes because of Covid-19 lockdowns.

Table 3. Extent of parents' support on learners amidst the pandemic

Parents Support	Learners*						Parents**					
	Central School (n =114)		Non-Central School (n = 242)		As a whole		Central School (n =114)		Non-Central School (n = 242)		As a whole	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Regularly gets the modules from school at the scheduled time of the week.	4.31	VH E	4.21	VH E	4.24	VH E	4.21	VH E	4.24	VH E	4.23	VH E
Discusses the content of the module to be studied.	3.64	HE	3.53	HE	3.57	HE	3.79	HE	3.83	HE	3.82	HE
Encourages to completely answer the learning modules assigned each week.	4.33	VH E	4.08	HE	4.16	HE	4.44	VH E	4.31	VH E	4.35	VH E
Help understand specific assignments,	4.21	VH E	3.86	HE	3.97	HE	4.17	HE	4.10	HE	4.12	HE

activities, and outputs to be done.	3.88	HE	3.90	HE	3.90	HE	4.22	VH	4.09	HE	4.13	HE
Help follow the plan of time in answering the module.	4.05	HE	4.00	HE	4.02	HE	4.08	E	4.11	HE	4.10	HE
Helps in reading particular words that are not familiar.	3.92	HE	3.68	HE	3.76	HE	3.94	HE	3.88	HE	3.90	HE
Listens to reading and studying the content of the module.	3.82	HE	3.75	HE	3.77	HE	3.95	HE	3.93	HE	3.94	HE
Discusses the feeling and letting understand the new normal set-up of learning.	3.93	HE	3.84	HE	3.87	HE	3.97	HE	3.93	HE	3.95	HE
Has been actively engaged in studying from home.	4.00	HE	3.83	HE	3.88	HE	4.05	HE	4.00	HE	4.02	HE
Gives incentives like rewards or praises whenever a task in the module is completed.												
Grand Mean												

SD = Standard Deviation
VI = Verbal Interpretation

Table 3 indicated that parents of the learners display a high extent of support amidst the pandemic as perceived by both the learners ($M = 3.88$) and their parents ($M = 4.02$). Per item analysis tells us that both learners and parents perceived parents' support in terms of getting the modules in the scheduled time of the week regularly to a very high extent. While parents say that they have a very high extent of support ($M = 4.35$) in terms of encouraging the learners to answer the module assigned in a week completely; learners perceived that their parents supported them on a high extent ($M = 4.14$) in this area. Both learners and parents perceived a high extent of parents support in the following areas: discussing the content of the module to be studied; helping understand specific assignments, activities, and outputs to be done; helping follow the plan of time in answering the module; helping in reading particular words that are not familiar; listening to reading and studying the content of the module; discussing the feeling and letting understand the new normal setup of learning; being actively engaged in studying from home; and, giving incentives like rewards or praises whenever a task in the module is completed. This implies that parents have strong support and assistance to their children's remote learning. This is supported by Manlangit et al., (2020), that parents are not to be substituted for teachers but rather to collaborate with them in implementing remote learning. Parents serve as facilitators in their homes, serving as the "*tagapagdaloy*" or channel, but they do not teach the subject content. In modular learning, their major duty is to develop a connection and guide the child. Parents, as more knowledgeable individuals, are also responsible for liaising with stakeholders such as teachers, barangay officials, and others to ensure that student has access to different materials and resources required of them.

Table 4. *Difference in the extent of teachers' support as assessed by the learners and the teachers*

Teachers' Support	p-value	Interpretation
Understandable instruction and clear work in the module are given and set.	0.000	Significant
Conducts home visitation regularly to follow up activities in the learning module.	0.000	Significant
Gives immediate feedback on the work done or completed.	0.000	Significant
Always remind me of the tasks in the module to be completed for the	0.000	Significant

week.

Makes sure that the scheduled class program on studying from home is followed.	0.000	Significant
Gives additional resources (online interactive games, videos, articles) to further understand what is in the module.	0.410	Not Significant
Raising questions and concerns about the modules in an available communication platform.	0.000	Significant
Asks feelings and ideas about the module at hand (i.e. if it's difficult or easy).	0.000	Significant
Have enough time available for learners who are struggling to answer the modules by directing them what to do and how to accomplish it.	0.000	Significant
Collaborates with learners' parents on the study-from-home scheme.	0.000	Significant
Teachers' Support as a whole	0.000	Significant

It can be gleaned from Table 4 that the extent of teachers' support as assessed by learners and teachers differ significantly ($p = 0.0$) as a whole at a 0.05 level of significance. This implies that while teachers perceived that they extended very high support to their learners, learners feel the other way around. Detailed analysis shows that a significant difference exists in the extent of teachers' support as assessed by teachers and learners in all support parameters at a 0.05 level of significance. The p-value of all the items is 0.00 except for item 6, with a p-value of 0.41, which is not significant. The result rejects the null hypothesis that there exists no significant difference in the extent of teachers' support on academic stress as assessed by the learners and teachers is rejected. This implies that teachers' support to learners in their remote learning plays of great value in maintaining their sanity and academic stress except for the construct "teacher gives additional resources to further understand what is in the module. This is, of course, one effort done by teachers to reach out to the learners in their remote learning. In some cases, there may be times that it creates a disappointment to the learners because of the poor internet connection like glitches and slow loading of the videos, sometimes no internet connection available, weekly expenses for the internet load and non-availability of gadgets by the learners and among many others which exacerbates their cognitive stress.

Table 5. Difference in the extent of parents' support as assessed by the learners and the parents

Parents' Support	p-value	Interpretation
Regularly gets the modules from school at the scheduled time of the week.	0.870	Not Significant
Discusses the content of the module to be studied.	0.002	Significant
Encourages to completely answer the learning modules assigned each week.	0.005	Significant
Helps understand specific assignments, activities, and outputs to be done.	0.076	Not Significant
Helps follow the plan of time in answering the module.	0.002	Significant
Helps in reading particular words that are not familiar.	0.300	Not Significant
Listens to reading and studying the content of the module.	0.063	Not Significant
Discusses the feeling and letting understand the new normal set-up of learning.	0.031	Significant
Has been actively engaged in studying from home.	0.311	Not Significant
Gives incentives like rewards or praises whenever a task in the module is completed.	0.223	Not Significant
Parents' Support as a whole	0.008	Significant

Table 5 revealed there is a significant difference ($p = 0.008$) in the extent of parents' support as assessed by the learners and by the parents at a 0.05 level of significance, the findings reject the null hypothesis that no significant difference exists in the extent of parents' support on academic stress as assessed by the learners, and their parents is rejected. It also reveals that specific significant differences exist in the extent of parents support as assessed by the learners and by the parents at a 0.05 level of significance in terms of discussing the content of the module to be studied ($p = 0.002$); encouraging to completely answer the learning modules assigned each week ($p = 0.005$); helping follow the plan of time in answering the module ($p = 0.002$); and, discussing the feeling and letting understand the new normal setup of learning ($p = 0.031$). The parents' support given to the learners on the four constructs mentioned above was not felt or observed by the learners from their perspective. In this sense, the efforts made and done by the parents to support their child/children are less likely to mitigate the difficulties encountered by the learners in their remote learning.

Table 6. *Correlation between learners' academic stress and teachers' support*

Academic Stress	Teachers support			
	As assessed by learners		As assessed by teachers	
	p-value	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Behavioral	0.087	Not Significant	0.458	Not Significant
Emotional	0.033	Significant	0.661	Not Significant
Physical	0.490	Not Significant	0.032	Significant
Cognitive	0.005	Significant	0.191	Not Significant
As a whole	0.033	Significant	0.201	Not Significant

Table 6 tells a significant correlation ($p = 0.033$) exists between learners' academic stress (as a whole) and teachers' support as assessed by learners themselves at a 0.05 level of significance. This strongly suggests that the lower the extent the support of the teachers is, the higher the academic stress the learner's experience. Meaning to say, if there is no teacher support, learners predominantly feel stress, burnout, and hopelessness in enduring their learning at home, significant correlation exist ($p = 0.033$) between emotional stress and the extent of teachers support as assessed by the learners; and cognitive stress ($p = 0.005$) and the extent of teachers support as assessed by learners which means, learners need their teachers' scaffold in carrying out their remote learning, more specifically in answering their modules. Teachers' support on this matter is highly regarded, and no one can replace that support. There is no significant ($p = .201$) correlation between learners' academic stress and teachers' support as assessed by teachers. However, it can be noted that significant correlation exist between physical stress and extent of teachers support as assessed by students ($p = 0.032$). This implies that on the teachers' part, it would be tedious on their part and taxing if they would go home visit and provide one on one tutelage and support to each of the pupils, thus affect their physical stress as well. Therefore, the findings respectively reject and accept the null hypothesis that no significant correlation exists between the level of academic stress and the extent of teachers' support is rejected and accepted.

Teachers are accountable for monitoring the learners' progress. Teachers can be reached via telephone, instant messaging, text message, or email, among other modes of communication. Wherever possible, the teacher will make home visits to students who need remediation or assistance at home (Llego, n.d.). This is supported by Sumaoang and Dangle (2020), who found out that 90% of participants struggled to complete their modules. Half of them lack time necessary to complete all of their programs within a week. Pupils frequently receive at least eight modules across all topics, with each module containing 3-5 tasks. Some of the concepts are also quite tough to comprehend, and several of the questions are challenging as well, with insufficient examples offered. Notably, the majority of learners are unable to complete their courses individually, which is why they rely heavily on the support of others. Teachers were accessible, although some did not respond swiftly to learners' questions about the lessons. It might be due to the bulk of modules checked, weekly home learning plans need to prepare, summative tests/ weekly tests, performance tasks, GRASPS activity, worksheets, and

supplemental videos and radio-based instruction and or Television-based instruction need to be done and taped to mitigate the difficulties encountered by the learners in understanding the concepts presented in the modules. But most of the time, the teacher sees to it that they provide substantial support to the learners who cannot pass and accomplish the module within the time frame by doing home visitations and tutorials to the at-risk pupils of dropping out. Teachers also answer parents' and learners' questions, clarifications, and queries from time to time through messaging with regards to the submission and retrieval of the said modules and the tasks that need to be accomplished. With all those adjustments and efforts, the support given to the learners has eased and lightened the burden and academic stress the learners may experience in learning at home.

Table 7. Correlation between learners' academic stress and parents' support

Academic Stress	Parents support			
	As assessed by learners		As assessed by parents	
	p-value	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Behavioral	0.087	Not Significant	0.901	Not Significant
Emotional	0.000	Significant	0.707	Not Significant
Physical	0.403	Not Significant	0.744	Not Significant
Cognitive	0.002	Significant	0.846	Not Significant
As a whole	0.008	Significant	0.826	Not Significant

The results from Table 7 reveal that there is a significant correlation ($p = 0.008$) between academic stress (as a whole) and the extent of parents' support as assessed by the learners. Table 7 shows significant correlation ($p = 0.000$) between emotional stress and the extent of parents' support as assessed by the learners; and between cognitive stress and the extent of parents' support ($p = 0.002$). Moreover, there is no significant correlation between academic stress of the learners and the extent of parents' support as perceived by their parents. Henceforth, the results reject the null hypothesis that no significant correlation is present between the level of academic stress and the extent of parents' support. This implies that the parents' support is of great blessings and help to the learners learning at home. This is supported by Sumaoang & Dangle (2020), where 54% of parents work, and 46% are unemployed. However, majority of working parents indicated that they have sufficient time to support their child/children academically in completing their courses. Learners' family members, relatives, and friends play a critical part in education nowadays because they act as a stress reliever for learners by assisting them in overcoming challenges they had while learning and answering the modules. Siblings are the primary source of assistance for learners, followed by friends and classmates. As a result, while not all parents achieve higher education, they ensure that their children receive the finest possible support. For parents, education is one of the most valuable commodities when it comes to securing a brighter future for their children.

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that learners from central and non-central schools are experiencing academic stress amidst pandemic at moderate level. The teachers' extent of support to the academic stress experienced by the learners differs from the observation claimed by the teachers. The extent of parents' support extended by the parents to learners as assessed by parents and learners themselves is too high. Home-based education of learners amidst the pandemic created a sense of stressors, burnouts, and disturbances to the cognitive and emotional well-being of the learners. The extent of teachers' supports and parents' support given to the learners is of great help and beneficial in alleviating the academic stress experienced by the learners in studying at home. Learners are not ready for independent learning and working at their own pace in studying from home, for they need guidance of their respective teachers and parents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Teachers' and parents' support, guidance, mentorship, and scaffolding to learners continuing education at home in these trying times of pandemic is recommended to be steadily strengthened and improved because it creates a huge impact on the learner's overall well-being and academic stress encountered in multiple distance learning delivery modalities. Parents and learners at home may adopt a coping strategy that is practical and applicable during remote learning, which can minimize the risk of psychological distress and preserve the health and well-being of their children. Teachers should religiously provide learners an open platform for communication where they can express their feelings and emotions, challenges and difficulties experienced and offer some counseling techniques, student wellness support, incorporation of daily "well-being checks," the inclusion of mindfulness in classes, and self-care tips to combat and manage the possible profound effect of academic stress. Teachers and parents may collaborate and synergize honest effort in making sure that the learner's needs and problems are addressed properly and given immediate solutions to mitigate the issue at hand. Teachers and parents may also strategize to reach out to their child/children to cope up with the challenging demands of remote learning by establishing a regular schedule to assist learners with the difficulties encountered. And lastly, learners are suggested to be open and honest to their parents, teachers, and elders about their present struggles, difficulties, and questions confronted at hand, which may hamper their mental health and progress in learning at home.

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